

THE CONTENT AND CONDITIONS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PERSON-DIRECTED EDUCATION IN THE EDUCATION PROCESS OF SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ANNOTATION: This article highlights **the content, requirements and conditions of the implementation of education on the basis of person-oriented approaches in the comprehensive development of preschool children through education .**

KEY WORDS: Pedagogical impact, reflection, self-awareness, humanism, need motivation, individuality, academic needs, didactic needs, socio-psychological needs, communicative basis, a new view of the individual, achievement environment.

In order to further improve the preschool education system, to ensure children's equal use of quality preschool education, to develop the non-state sector of preschool education services, it is also necessary to approve the concession for the development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2018 "On measures to improve the management of the preschool education system" PQ-4312 in" was accepted. In accordance with this concept, creating conditions for comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children, increasing the coverage of children with quality preschool education, ensuring equal access to it, developing public-private partnerships in this field, introducing innovations, advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the preschool education system, improving the management system of preschool education, ensuring the transparency and efficiency of financing the activities of preschool education organizations, the introduction of completely new approaches to training, retraining, professional development, selection and development of education system personnel was determined. The effective solution of these tasks, in turn , requires the creation of an innovative educational environment and the elimination of current problems and shortcomings through the development and implementation of new modern technologies in the educational process . Also, modern requirements indicate the need to modernize the educational process as a whole system and organize innovative activities in education.

Formation of a free and independent thinker, a broad-minded, creative person with intellectual potential who is loyal to our national ideology requires extensive use of the latest achievements of science and technology in the field of education. In solving this problem, it is important to be the driving force of the development of society, to develop information and to use it effectively for planned purposes. Therefore, it is one of the urgent tasks to ensure that the educational process is organized on the basis of personal educational technologies.

This requires developing the educational process with a different approach. We consider the possibility of fulfilling these requirements by organizing personalized education.

The theoretical foundations of person-centered education include:

- determination of the learner's place in the educational process and personality development;
- Normative requirements are set for the development of the learner. These standards are reflected in State requirements;
- creative ability and skills of the pedagogue are of great importance in organizing the educational process.
- the educational process requires the use of person-oriented educational technologies.

In person-oriented education, pedagogical effects are mainly focused on the development of the learner's personality. M.M. Bakhtin considered the person as an open system. He saw the incompleteness of man in the development of his consciousness, in reflection, in self-awareness, in the possibility of changing the point of view towards himself and continuing his development through these. Based on the humanitarian approach, he defined the person as an active system, that is, the person does not simply respond to external influences, but also has the ability to influence the environment actively and purposefully. In order to live as a person, a person must have a creative attitude to the world, develop his own personal view of it, set new tasks before him and solve them in new ways. According to A. Maslow, the emergence of new interests, the desire to acquire knowledge, a sense of responsibility - all these forms of life activity indicate the existence of "need motivation".

One of the main characteristics of a person is his individuality, because each person is unique and invaluable in his place. Individuality is "the most valuable thing in a person and his creativity", it is "manifested in the ability to do what everyone can do, giving everyone a new standard of work and doing it better than everyone else."

One of the main features that distinguish pedagogical technologies from each other is the level of orientation towards the child. At the center of personal-oriented technologies is a growing person, his desire to fully express his capabilities, to accept new experiences, to make conscious and responsible decisions in various life situations.

Personal development is carried out in order to prepare a creative person who meets the requirements of the world standard, who can express his right attitude to himself, another person, society, the state, nature and work, who can work independently, and create conditions for independent work and self-education.

They also recommend that they know the knowledge of the psychology of personality development and use it in their activities, know the academic, didactic, socio-psychological needs of preschool children in order to properly organize the educational process and organize activities taking into account these needs, can establish positive relationships with preschool children, know educational technologies and teaching methods, can develop general and individual-oriented rules during the activities it is very important to give

Pedagogical process increases the possibilities of pre-guaranteeing the achievement of implementation-educational goals on the basis of person-oriented technologies.

The communicative basis of person-oriented technologies is considered to be a "new look at the person" in the pedagogical process, that is, a human-personal approach, which includes:

- pedagogical process a person is not an object, but a subject;
- each one education receiver ability owner, majority while talent the owner is _

- high ethical values (generosity , love , diligence , conscience and others)
of the person priority characteristics is considered

Education in the process relationships democratization the following includes :
education _ _ receiver and pedagogic rights equalization , education of the recipient free
choose get the right to the error road to put the right own point of view have to be right
pedagogue and education receiver attitude basis to be , that is :

- a) non-prohibition ;
- c) management not together _ management ;
- c) coercion not , persuasion ;
- d) ordering not organized _ reach _
- e) limitation not , free choose to get possibility to give

Above note done new of relationships main content present developed and more fast
pictures with developing one conditions efficient result does not give and not human
considered force from abandoning pedagogy consists of

Modern in the circumstances education of the process all opportunities according to
person development , socialization and in it independent , critical , creative thinking abilities
to educate orientation demand is being done . In itself these opportunities _ was able to show
education to the individual directed education that is called

To the person directed education - of the learner thinking and movement strategy in
consideration received without his person , to himself special characteristics , ability to
develop directed education _

This implies that the learning environment is adapted to the capabilities of the learner.
According to him, the educational environment, pedagogical conditions, education and
upbringing process fully realize the personal potential of the learner, develop his abilities,
ensure his maturation as a person, and enrich his thinking and worldview.

A unique aspect of person-oriented education is **to recognize the learner's personality**, to create a comfortable and necessary environment for his comprehensive
development.

This type of education serves to educate pre-school children such qualities as
independence, initiative, responsibility, as well as independent, creative and critical thinking
skills. In the organization of this type of education, pedagogues are required to approach each
learner as individually as possible, respect his personality, and show confidence in him.

MTTs, pedagogues should strictly adhere to a number of conditions when using person-
oriented types of education in the process of education. These requirements include:

- being able to see each preschooler as a separate, unique person;
- respect for preschool children;
- ability to correctly assess the mental state of preschool children;
- taking into account the wishes and interests of preschool children;
- each one tolerant to a preschool child in relation to be
- power and opportunity of preschool children and to their aspirations trust to express ;
- each one for preschool children comfortable education environment to create ;
- before school age of children independent or small to groups free their performance
for chance create ;

- before school age the children own activities independent control doing , activity efficiency determination of achievements factors and road placed of mistakes consequences analysis to do to teach
- education in the process never one education to the recipient pressure impenetrability ;
- separately education of the recipient disadvantages exaggerated do not show ;
- bordi -yu, a preschooler by competencies master not getting , education in the process himself rude catch status note if , then strictly conclusion without taking it out reasons to determine
- determined reasons based on before school age of children honor , pride loss did not deliver by him without knowledge master not to get , himself rude catch like circumstances eliminate reach _
- education in the process each one " success " for a preschool child environment". create get _
- each one education for preschool children to get to success reach to get help to give - education of the recipient ability Cultivation , person as development help to give

To the person directed education education recipient education system as a pedagogue each one education of the recipient respect and confidence win take adaptation not , on the contrary , its individual characteristics in consideration received without each bilaterally development , personality as to maturity reach for necessary conditions to create mean holds _ This stay education before school age the children self to develop , independent knowledge to get , one's own internal possibilities , abilities full to be able to show , to know activity increase for necessary the conditions to the body to bring necessary _ Before school age children to the individual directed education in the process information to master creative , critical approach , new ideas before push them _ justification , own his opinion protection make , problematic situations efficient the solution to find skills , qualifications appropriation opportunity have will be

in MTTs education in the process of the following use to the individual directed of education again one is the symbol :

- creative assignments ;
- creative approach requirement doer duties ;
- problematic situations ;
- role and entrepreneurship games ;
- debate , debate ;
- competition in the form of competitions and others.

The main goal of child-oriented education is to include the mechanisms of self-awareness, development, adaptation, management, protection, education necessary for the unique formation of the child

References:

1. Decision No. PQ-4312 "On approval of the concept of development of preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030"
2. Gayduchenok I.A. Slovo o lichnosti: Philosophical essay // Minsk: Nauka i tekhnika, 1990. - 157p.

- 3.Maslow A. Novye rubeji chelovecheskoy prirody/ pod ed.G.A. Balla, A.N. Leonteva. - M. : Smysl, 1999. - 425p.
- 4.Olimov K.T. Person-oriented learning technologies// Vocational education. #3. 2007.
- 5.Ilenkov E.V. Philosophy and culture / E.V. Ilenkov. - M. : Izd. political literature, 1991.— 463 p
- 6.<http://tmatm.uz/site/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/2.-SAHASGA-JUNALTIRILGAN-TALIM-TYRULARI-VA.pdf>
- 7.F.R. Valieva The importance of educational content in preparation of competitive personnel // 2 nd International Conference BRIDGE TO SCIENCE: RESEARCH WORKS San Francisco, USA February 28, 2018
- 8.Valieva F.R, Muminjanov A.S. GLOBALNYE PROBLEMY EKOLOGII ./ Voprosy nauki i obrazovaniya No. 5 (50), 2019 / <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.ru>

